

Reactions of Ferric Isopropoxide with Glycols and Catechol

P. P. Sharma and R. C. Mehrotra

Reactions of ferric isopropoxide with diols (e.g ethane; propane-1,2-and-1,3-; butane-2, 3-; -1,3-; -1,4- and pentane-1,5-diols, pinacol and hexylene glycol) and catechol have been carried out in different stoichiometric ratios and the following two types of new derivatives $(\text{Pr}^i\text{O})\text{Fe}\begin{matrix} \diagup \text{O} \\ \diagdown \text{O} \end{matrix}\text{R}$ and $\text{R}\begin{matrix} \text{H} \\ \diagup \text{O} \\ \diagdown \text{O} \end{matrix}\text{Fe}\begin{matrix} \diagup \text{O} \\ \diagdown \text{O} \end{matrix}\text{R}$

have been isolated. The diglycollates of butane-2,3-diol, pinacol and hexylene glycol on heating under reduced pressure lose a molecule of glycol intermolecularly yielding diferric triglycollates. Molecular weights of a few soluble glycollates were also determined in refluxing benzene.

Weinland and Binder¹ in 1912, studied the reactions of ferric chloride and pyrocatechol in alkaline solution. In 1929 Selles² isolated two types of complexes, one violet, $\text{M}[\text{Fe}(\text{Cat.})_2]$ and the other red, $\text{M}_3[\text{Fe}(\text{Cat.})_3]$, solid. Recently, a potentiometric investigation of iron (III) glycollates has been carried out by Cadriu and Andil³. In last few years, an appreciable amount of work has been published from these laboratories on the glycol and catechol derivatives of a number of elements⁴⁻¹⁹. A careful survey of the literature revealed that so far no work has been reported on the reactions of ferric alkoxides with glycols.

The reaction of glycols with ferric isopropoxide in 1:1 molar ratio in the presence of benzene can be represented by the equation :

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2. E. Selles, *Anal. Fis. Quim.*, 1929, **27**, 569.
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15. S. N. Mathur and R. C. Mehrotra, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 814; 1965, **42**, 749.
16. R. K. Mittal and R. C. Mehrotra, (Private Communication).
17. P. N. Kapoor and R. C. Mehrotra, *J. Less-common Metals*, 1965, **8**, 419.
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19. T. N. Misra, S. N. Misra and R. C. Mehrotra, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (In press).

The reaction was followed by distilling azeotropically along with benzene and estimating the isopropanol produced during the reaction. It has been found that derivatives of ethane-diol, propane-1, 2-and -1,3-diols, butane-1,4-diol and pentane-1,5- diol were insoluble in benzene whereas the corresponding derivatives of butane-2,3-and-1,3-diols and pinacol and hexylene glycol were soluble. The reaction of propane-1,3-diol was also studied in 1:1 molar ratio at the room temperature and a monoglycollate derivative was obtained.

Similarly, reactions of ferric isopropoxide with glycols mentioned above were also studied in the molar ratio, 1:2 and in all cases, except pinacol and hexylene glycol, yellowish brown solids were separated from benzene.

The above observed variations in the solubility in organic solvents of various diol derivatives is quite interesting ; it may be worthwhile to mention that even the parent free glycols show a similar trend in their solubility in hydrocarbon solvents.

Diglycollate derivatives of butane-2,3-diol, pinacol and hexylene glycol undergo intermolecular change on heating under reduced pressure and lose a molecule of glycol to give diferric triglycollates. These derivatives were also prepared by the reaction of ferric isopropoxide with butane-2,3-diol, pinacol and hexylene glycol in the molar ratio 2:3:

Molecular weights of some benzene soluble compounds were determined ebullioscopically and it has been found that monoisopropoxide monoglycollates were dimeric in nature while diglycollates were monomeric. The presence of an acidic hydrogen atom in diglycollate derivatives has been shown by treating a benzene solution of Fe (hexylene glycol)₂ with anhydrous ammonia when an exothermic reaction took place and a yellow compound corresponding to NH₄⁺ [Fe (hexylene glycol)₂]⁻ in analysis was isolated on drying the solvent under reduced pressure.

The reactions of ferric isopropoxide with all glycols mentioned earlier were also carried out in the molar ratio 1:3. In all cases, completely dry solid products were obtained which gave no apparent indication of the unreacted glycol. On analysis these compounds were found to be triglycollates. These compounds were washed with an excess of the solvent (in which the parent glycol was soluble like benzene or ethyl alcohol) when compounds corresponding to the diglycollate derivatives were obtained.

For the sake of comparison, it was considered of interest to carry out reactions of ferric isopropoxide with catechol. Reactions were found to follow a similar pattern :

EXPERIMENTAL

Apparatus and chemicals : All glass apparatus fitted with interchangeable joints was used and special precautions being taken to exclude moisture. All fractionations were carried out in a column packed with Raschig rings and fitted to a total condensation variable-takeoff stillhead.

Molecular weights were determined ebullioscopically in boiling benzene by a semi-micro Gallenkamp ebullimeter. Reagents were dried and ferric isopropoxide was prepared as reported in an earlier communication²⁰. The glycols were purified by distillation before use.

Analytical Method : Iron was estimated as Fe_2O_3 and isopropanol oxidimetrically²¹ and a correction for ferric was applied in the latter case.

Ethane, propane-1,2-and butane-2,3-diols were estimated²² with sodium pericdate by the "Malaprade method"²³. Nitrogen was estimated by the well-known Kjeldahl's method.

Reaction between ferric isopropoxide and ethylene glycol (molar ratio 1:1) : Ethylene glycol (0.35 g) was added to a solution of ferric isopropoxide (1.57 g) in benzene (80.0g). On shaking, no noticeable amount of heat appeared to be produced. The reaction mixture was refluxed under a column for about an hour at a bath temperature of 110-120°. As soon as a few ml of azeotrope of the liberated isopropanol with solvent benzene was collected at 72-80°, a yellowish brown solid began to separate on the walls of the reaction vessel. The remaining solvent was distilled at a high reflux ratio. After cooling the product was freed from solvent under reduced pressure and the compound was finally dried at 30°/0.2 mm for three hours to yield a yellowish brown solid (1.00 g) insoluble in benzene.

Found : isopropanol in the azeotrope, 0.69 g (2 moles require, 0.70 g).

Found : Fe, 32.79; glycoxy, 33.82%. Calc. for $\text{Fe}(\text{OPri})(\text{ethylene glycol})$: Fe, 31.92; glycoxy, 34.34%.

Reaction between Fe (hexylene glycol)₂ and anhydrous ammonia : An exothermic reaction was observed on passing anhydrous ammonia in a benzene (40.0 g) solution of the above compound (0.32 g). A yellow solid (2.38 g) soluble in benzene was obtained when the excess of benzene was removed under reduced pressure at 35°/0.2 mm.

Found : Fe, 18.30; N, 4.51%. Calc. for $\text{NH}_4^+ [\text{Fe}(\text{hexylene glycol})_2]$ Fe, 18.24; N, 4.57%.

For brevity other reactions are tabulated in tables I, II and III.

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21. D. C. Bradley and W. Wardlaw, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 3450.

22. P. P. Sharma, Ph.D. Thesis, Rajasthan University, Jaipur, 1966.

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TABLE I (cont.)

Reactants	(g)	Molar ratio	Product and state	Amount of		Analysis %				Mol. Wt.	
				alcohol in azeotrope Found(g)	Found(g) Calc.	Iron Found	Glycoxy Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	
Fe (OPr ⁱ) ₃	(1.94)	1:1	(OPr ⁱ) Fe (hexylene glycol)	0.99	1.01	24.27	24.17	—	—	465	231
Hexylene glycol	(0.99)		Brown solid soluble in benzene (1.79 g)		two moles						
Benzene	(70.0)										
Fe (OPr ⁱ) ₃	(2.80)	1:1	(OPr ⁱ) Fe (Catechol)	1.38	1.44	25.41	25.05	26.07	26.51	—	—
Catechol	(1.32)		Black solid insoluble in benzene (2.56 g)		three moles						
Benzene	(65.0)										
Fe (OPr ⁱ) ₃	(1.15)	1:2	Fe (ethylene glycol) ₂	0.88	0.89	32.61	31.51	66.55	68.45	—	—
Ethylene glycol	(0.59)		Yellowish brown solid insoluble in benzene (0.81 g)		three moles						
Benzene	(80.0)										
Fe (OPr ⁱ) ₃	(2.52)	1:2	Fe (propane-1,2-diol) ₂	1.82	1.94	27.33	27.24	71.83	72.73	—	—
Propane-1,2-diol	(1.64)		Yellowish brown solid insoluble in benzene (2.11 g)		three moles						
Benzene	(75.0)										
Fe (OPr ⁱ) ₄	(3.21)	1:2	Fe (propane-1,3-diol) ₂	2.40	2.48	27.36	27.24	—	—	—	—
Propane-1,3-diol	(2.10)		Yellowish brown solid insoluble in benzene (2.80 g)		three moles						
Benzene	(80.0)										
Fe (OPr ⁱ) ₃	(1.50)	1:2	Fe (butane-2, 3-diol) ₂	1.15	1.16	24.35	23.95	75.25	76.03	—	—
Butane-2, 3-diol	(1.16)		Brown solid insoluble in benzene (1.41 g)		three moles						
Benzene	(70.0)										
Fe (OPr ⁱ) ₃	(3.66)	1:1.5	Fe ₂ (butane-2, 3-diol) ₃	2.33	2.24	29.76	29.70	69.47	70.30	—	—
Butane-2, 3-diol	(2.12)		Brown solid insoluble in benzene (2.87g)		three moles						
Benzene	(60.0)										
Fe (OPr ⁱ) ₃	(2.60)	1:2	Fe (butane-1,3-diol) ₂	1.58	1.60	24.16	23.95	—	—	—	—
Butane-1,3-diol	(2.01)		Brown solid insoluble in benzene (3.76 g)		three moles						
Benzene	(80.0)										
Fe (OPr ⁱ) ₃	(0.54)	1:2	Fe(butane-1,4-diol)	0.43	0.42	24.06	23.95	—	—	—	—
Butane-1, 4-diol	(0.42)		Yellowish Brown solid insoluble in benzene (0.53 g)		three moles						
Benzene	(60.0)										

TABLE I (contd.)

Reactants	(g)	Molar ratio	Product and state	Amount of		Analysis %		Mol. Wt.	
				Alcoholin	azetrope	Iron	Glycoxy	Found	Calc.
				Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
Fe (OPr ⁱ) ₃	(2.03)	1:2	Fe (pentane-1, 5-diol) ₂	1.56	1.57	21.32	21.40	—	—
Pentane-1, 5-diol	(1.83)		Yellowish brown solid insoluble in benzene (2.20 g)	three moles					
Benzene	(70.0)								
Fe (OPr ⁱ) ₃	(1.55)	1:2	Fe (pinacol) ₂	1.19	1.21	19.41	19.32	—	—
Pinacol	(1.57)		Brown solid soluble in benzene (1.88 g)	three moles				293	289
Benzene	(65.0)								
Fe (OPr ⁱ) ₃	(3.06)	1:1.5	Fe ₂ (pinacol) ₃	2.32	2.37	24.31	24.26	—	—
Pinacol	(2.33)		Yellowish brown solid soluble in benzene (2.93 g)	three moles				473	460
Benzene	(70.0)								
Fe (OPr ⁱ) ₃	(2.03)	1:2	Fe (hexylene glycol) ₂	1.48	1.57	20.06	19.32	—	—
Hexylene glycol	(2.06)		Brown solid soluble in benzene (2.45 g)	three moles				290	289
Benzene	(76.0)								
Fe (OPr ⁱ) ₃	(4.32)	1:1.5	Fe ₂ (hexylene glycol) ₂	3.32	3.33	24.32	24.26	—	—
Hexylene glycol	(3.28)		Yellow solid soluble in benzene (4.13 g)	three moles				469	460
Benzene	(70.0)								
Fe (OPr ⁱ) ₃	(1.61)	1:2	Fe (Catechol) ₂	1.23	1.24	20.51	20.46	—	—
Catechol	(1.51)		Black solid insoluble in benzene (1.84 g)	three moles				—	—
Benzene	(70.0)								

*Reaction was carried out at the room temperature.

TABLE II

Action of heat on Fe (glycol)₂

Compound	(g)	Condition	Product and State	Analysis%			
				Iron Found	Iron Calc.	Glycoxy Found	Glycoxy Calc.
Fe (butane-2,3-diol) ₂	(0.98)	Heated at 105° /0.2mm	Fe ₂ (butane-2,3-diol) ₃ Brown solid insoluble in benzene (0.80 g)	29.64	29.70	69.5	70.30
Fe (pinacol) ₂	(1.12)	Heated at 115° /0.3mm	Fe ₂ (pinacol) ₃ Yellowish brown solid soluble in benzene (0.89 g)	24.29	24.26	—	—
Fe (hexylene glycol) ₂	(1.96)	Heated at 97° /0.2mm	Fe ₂ (hexylene glycol) ₃ Yellow solid soluble in benzene (1.56 g)	24.32	24.26	—	—

TABLE III

Reactions of ferric isopropoxide with glycols and catechol (molar ratio 1:3)

Reactants	(g)	Product and State	Amount of alcohol in azeotrope (g) Found Calc.		Analysis %							
					Before washing				After washing			
					Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
Fe (OPr ⁱ) ₃	(0.68)	Fe (ethylene glycol) ₃	0.49	0.53	24.28	23.36	75.46	76.65	31.78	31.57	68.23	68.45
Ethylene glycol	(0.53)	Yellowish brown solid		three moles								
Benzene	(50.0)	insoluble in benzene (1.68g)										
Fe (OPr ⁱ) ₃	(1.42)	Fe (propane-1, 2-diol) ₃	0.99	1.09	19.95	19.86	78.93	80.11	27.03	27.24	73.64	72.73
Propane-1, 2-diol	(1.39)	Yellowish brown solid insoluble in benzene (1.64 g)		three moles								
Benzene	(80.0)											
Fe (OPr ⁱ) ₃	(1.95)	Fe (propane-1, 3-diol) ₃	1.44	1.51	20.00	19.86	—	—	27.19	27.24	—	—
Propane-1, 3-diol	(1.91)	Yellowish brown solid insoluble in benzene (2.33 g)		three moles								
Benzene	(80.0)											
Fe (OPr ⁱ) ₃	(1.14)	Fe (butane-2, 3-diol) ₃	0.86	0.88	17.53	17.27	81.51	82.71	23.81	23.96	77.38	76.03
Butane-2, 3-diol	(1.16)	Brown solid insoluble in benzene (1.47 g)		three moles								
Benzene	(60.0)											
Fe (OPr ⁱ) ₃	(1.29)	Fe (butane-1, 3-diol) ₃	0.98	1.00	17.58	17.27	—	—	23.77	23.96	—	—
Butane-1, 3-diol	(1.50)	Brown solid insoluble in benzene (1.72g)		three moles								
Benzene	(80.0)											
Fe (OPr ⁱ) ₃	(1.04)	Fe (butane-1, 4-diol) ₃	0.77	0.80	17.61	17.27	—	—	24.02	23.96	—	—
Butane-1, 4-diol	(1.20)	Yellowish brown solid insoluble in benzene (1.41 g)		three moles								
Benzene	(80.0)											
Fe (OPr ⁱ) ₃	(2.54)	Fe (Pentane-1, 5-diol) ₃	1.95	1.96	15.23	15.30	—	—	21.12	21.40	—	—
Pentane-1, 5-diol	(3.43)	Yellowish brown solid insoluble in benzene (4.00 g)		three moles								
Benzene	(70.0)											
Fe (OPr ⁱ) ₃	(1.94)	Fe (catechol) ₃	1.40	1.41	14.21	14.57	—	—	20.07	20.46	—	—
Catechol	(2.59)	Black solid insoluble in benzene (1.79 g)		three moles								
Benzene	(70.0)											

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